

INTERACTION: IT'S EFFECTS IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS SECOND LANGUAGE IN CLASSROOM

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Abstract:

In the process of acquiring a second language many suitable methods are being adopted by both learners and teachers in the classroom. It is normally acknowledged that classroom interaction is said to be fruitful for language learning. Effective cognitive developments take place among the learners in the process of interaction in the classroom. Long's (1991) psycholinguistic perspective has been used to assess the effectiveness of the acquisition of language through interaction. The significant part of this theoretical structure is how the learners learn through negotiation of meaning. There are different aspects that deal with in the negotiation of meaning. But the discussion has been focused on only two; repetition and recast. The data have been collected through thorough examination and student's interrogation. They were collected on the basis of the role played by recast and repetition in the process of facilitating the language learner.

Key Words: Interaction, Psycholinguistic Perspective, Negotiation of Meaning, Recast & Repetition

Introduction:

In the recent past many research have been done in order to analyze the significance of classroom interaction when learners are acquiring a second language. These research paid attention to the role of negotiation in language learning and comparing tasks have been undertaken individually as well as cooperatively. When dealing with second language acquisition it is important to pay attention to several factors which may motivate and facilitate learner's acquisition.

Interaction is considered important word for the ESL (English as a Second Language) teachers. "In the era of communicative language teaching, interaction is, in fact, the heart of communication; it is what communication is all about (Brown, H.D. 1994)".

CLT (Communicative Language Teaching) stress on interaction as people use language to negotiate meaning in various situations. Interaction helps student to come out with what they have already learnt from classroom or from the real life situations. Relevant literature has been integrated after thorough classroom observations of active participation of the learners towards learning English in the classroom.

1. Account of the Learning Place:

The sample place, which was taken for the study, was classroom accomplished with a personal computer, a LCD Projector, a white board, a phonetics chart, a chart of pictures and furnished furniture. The stage set for the teacher and learner was visible for all the students sitting. The classroom compact enough that there was no hindrance and eco in the process of interaction. Everybody felt cozy and comfort in the classroom ambiance.

2. Target Learners:

Learner1 (L1), a boy of 19 years old was involved with learner2 (L2), a girl of 24 years old in interaction in the classroom ambiance. In the observation it was found that L1 was quiet interested than L2. L1 was quiet interested because his apprenticeship kindled his eagerness to learn the language whereas L2 was limited with words as she knows the language quiet well than the L1.

3. Views about Interaction:

Wagner (1994: pp8) defines interaction as "reciprocal events that require at least two objects and two actions. Interaction occurs when these objects and events naturally influence one another". Therefore, interactions do not occur only from one side, there must be a mutual influence through giving and receiving messages in order to achieve communication.

Thurmond & Wambach (2004: pp4) states that: "The learner's engagement with the course content, other learners, the instructor and the technological medium used in the course. True interactions with other learners, the instructor and technology result in a reciprocal exchange of information. The exchange of information intended to enhance knowledge development in the learning environment."

It is inferred from the above quotation that there are four types of interaction, learner-course content interaction, learner-learner interaction, learner-teacher interaction and learner-technology interaction. But in this study, learner-learner interaction and learner-teacher interaction were being dealt.

According to Long (1996: pp. 413) "The most valuable way input is made comprehensible is through interactional adjustments. These are the attempts of learners and their conversation partners to overcome

comprehension difficulties so that incomprehensible or partly comprehensible input becomes comprehensible through negotiating of meaning. So learner learns through negotiation of meaning.”

Ellis and Barkhuizen (2005) define, “Negotiation of meaning as the verbal exchanges that occur when the speakers try to prevent the breakdown of the communication.”

4. Interaction by Means of Recast and Repetition:

Study 1 (S2), *Recast* (learner-learner interaction) and Study 2 (S2), *Repetition* (learner-teacher interaction) had been implemented and evaluated in the study.

4.1 Recast:

Study 1(S1)

Lyster and Ranta (1997) define, “Recast as a type of feedback in which the teacher implicitly reformulates student’s error or provides correction without directly indicating that the utterance was incorrect.”

Nicholas et al (2001: pp732-733) elaborate, “Recasts are the utterances that repeat a learner’s incorrect utterance, making only the changes necessary to produce a correct utterance, without changing the meaning.”

The technique of recasting is used in language teaching to correct learners’ errors in such a way that communication is not blocked. To recast an error, an interlocutor use to repeat the error back to the learner in a corrected form. Recasts are used both by teachers in formal educational settings, and by interlocutors in naturalistic language acquisition.

The following evidence shows the correction of errors in the process of recasting.

L2: When did you go for shopping last week?

L1: I goed last Sunday. [An erroneous utterance]

L2: I went last Sunday? [A recast]

In this example, the recast informed the learner of both positive evidence (form ‘went’ is grammatical) and negative evidence (form ‘goed’ is ungrammatical). So the L1 noticed error and easily learnt correct English.

It had been observed in S1 that many such mistakes like grammatical errors, phonological errors had been corrected through recasting which was more effective that took a course of days for L1 to correct himself through this method.

4.2 Repetition:

Study2 (S2)

Repetition is the saying by one individual of the spoken vocalizations made by another individual. This requires the ability in the person making the copy to map the sensory input they hear from the other person’s vocal pronunciation into a similar motor output with their own vocal tract.

According to Skehan (1998) “ In acquisitional terms, repetition in conversation can serve to consolidate what is being learned, Since the conversation may act as an unobtrusive but an effective scaffold for what is causing learning difficulty.”

In the same way

Lyster (1998: P187) consider repetition “as a means of fostering conceptual understanding.”

In S2 it has been observed that through repetition learners were engaged in conversation that paved way to understand their mistakes and to correct.

Teacher: “Do you have any beautiful pet?”

L1: Yes, I have a beauty dog.

Teacher: Oh! You have a beautiful dog. Where is the beautiful dog?

L1: The beautiful dog is at home.

Through this conversation it is understood that L1 learned the correct usage through conversation. The teacher didn’t correct the mistake but repeated the correct word ‘beautiful’ instead of the incorrect word ‘beauty’.

According to Knutson (2010), “pedagogically, repetition contributes to fluency and allows even low-fluency speakers to maintain face, and stay in the game. Repetition can be useful for communicative purposes.”

Teacher: “Do you play cricket?”

L1: Yes, I yesterday play cricket.

Teacher: Fine. You play cricket. Do you play every day or on holidays?

L1: I play every day in the evening.

The syntactical error in the sentence construction had been corrected through the above mentioned conversation between the teacher and L1.

According to Mackey (2007: 30) “through interaction that involves feedback, the attention of the learners are paid to the form of errors and are pushed to create modification.”

Conclusion:

From S1 and S2 it is understood that through interaction especially by means of repetition and recast L1 learnt English by noticing and correcting his errors. Recast helped him know correct usage of English and

repetition helped him both in learning and speaking by correcting errors like childhood language learning. Thus it is found that interaction is one of the effective strategies to improve communicative part of English language.

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